

Ischemic Stroke Revealing a Pituitary Macroadenoma: An Exceptional Clinical Case

K. Gorgi^{1*} and M. Chaouche²

¹Department of Endocrinology, CHP of Tata University Hospital, Rabat, Morocco

²Department of Dermatology, Mohammed VI University Hospital, Agadir, Morocco

WebLog Open Access Publications

Article ID - wjed.2026.b0704
Author : Dr. Khaoula Gorgi

Introduction

Ischemic strokes associated with pituitary adenomas are rare events, mostly reported in the context of pituitary apoplexy [1, 2]. We report a unique clinical case of a pituitary macroadenoma revealed by a pontine ischemic stroke.

Case Report

An 83-year-old female patient with a 5-year history of hypertension presented to the emergency department with sudden onset of right-sided hemiparesis. Brain MR angiography revealed a recent ischemic stroke in the left paramedian pontine area within the territory of the perforating branches of the basilar artery, associated with an intra- and suprasellar lesion measuring 21x14x18 mm, contacting the optic chiasm with left deviation of the pituitary stalk. Additionally, Fazekas grade 2 leukoencephalopathy was noted. Ophthalmological examination showed no visual field defects. Endocrine evaluation revealed no deficits. The patient was started on Dostinex (2 mg/week).

Conclusion

Management of non-functioning pituitary macroadenomas in elderly patients remains challenging, particularly when complicated by neurological events such as ischemic strokes [3, 4]. This case highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to optimize patient outcomes.

References

1. Petersenn S, Flitsch J, Saeger W. Pituitary adenomas and cerebrovascular disease: a review of clinical and pathological findings. *Pituitary*. 2021;24(3):317-327.
2. Mizuno H, Koyama J, Saito N. Cerebral infarction caused by pituitary apoplexy: clinical features and management. *Neurosurg Rev*. 2020; 43(4): 1003-1011.
3. Bruno A, Severino P, Papi G. Stroke in patients with pituitary tumors: a rare but challenging association. *J Endocrinol Invest*. 2022; 45(7): 1253-1262.
4. Gupta S, Thakur JD, Khurana A. Ischemic stroke as presenting manifestation of pituitary macroadenoma: a rare clinical entity. *Neurol India*. 2019; 67(2): 525-527.

OPEN ACCESS

*Correspondence:

Dr. Gorgi Khaoula, Department of Endocrinology and Metabolic Diseases, CHP of Tata University Hospital, Rabat, Morocco; Tel: 0615591874;

E-mail: khaoulagorgi@gmail.com

Received Date: 07 Jan 2026

Accepted Date: 05 Feb 2026

Published Date: 07 Feb 2026

Citation:

K. Gorgi, M. Chaouche. Ischemic Stroke Revealing a Pituitary Macroadenoma: An Exceptional Clinical Case. *WebLog J Endocrinol Diabetes*. wjed.2026.b0704. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18760984>

Copyright© 2026 Dr. Gorgi Khaoula. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.